

Study of the Spectral and Thermal Properties and Calculation of the Potential Energy of the Hydrogen Fluoride Molecule (HF) Using Semi-Empirical Quantum Programs

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ABSTRACT:

In this research, the potential energy and vibrational frequency of the linear molecule (HF) were studied and calculated using semi-empirical theoretical programs by the (MNDO-PM3) method. The spatial geometric structure of the studied molecule was plotted. The potential energy curve of the molecule was drawn based on the change in bond length (H—F) versus the obtained energy values. From this, the total energy at the equilibrium position was calculated and was (-133.755 eV) at an equilibrium distance of (0.93 Å). From the potential curve, the dissociation energy of the molecule was calculated and found to be (-131.454 eV). Additionally, the energy values of molecular orbitals, including the highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}), were calculated, with an energy gap of 19.784 eV. From the initial and final matrices, the thermal properties were calculated at varying temperatures between (100-300 K), and the graphical relationship of each property with temperature was plotted. The results were close to previous experimental studies.

Keywords: Energy gap, Equilibrium distance, Dissociation energy.

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen fluoride (HF) is one of the simplest diatomic covalent compounds and one of the most important from physical and chemical perspectives. The molecule consists of a hydrogen atom bonded to a fluorine atom by a strong and polar covalent bond resulting from the large electronegativity difference between the two atoms, which gives it distinctive properties compared to other hydrogen halides. The HF molecule is characterized by a high ability to form hydrogen bonds between its molecules, which explains its high boiling point compared to what is expected for a small molecule. The bond energy between H—F is among the highest in hydrogen halides, granting it great thermal stability and making it a reference in spectroscopic and thermal studies. Additionally, the HF molecule exhibits clear transitions in vibrational spectra due to its high dipole moment, making it an ideal substance for study in chemistry, physics, and thermodynamics. HF is used in the manufacture of fluorides, glass etching, and heat-resistant polymers, and when dissolved in water, it forms hydrofluoric acid [1-3].

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Theory

The total number of energy levels for any molecule is very large; therefore, some simplifications are necessary for explanation and various purposes. It seems appropriate to treat the molecule as if it consists of several distinct energy reservoirs, with the total energy divided among them according to the equation:

$$E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{trans}} + E_{\text{N.O}} + E_{\text{Rot}} + E_{\text{vib}} + E_{\text{elec}} \quad (1)$$

Where E_{trans} represents the translational kinetic energy, E_{Rot} represents rotational energy, $E_{\text{N.O}}$ represents nuclear orientation energy, E_{elec} electronic energy, and E_{vib} vibrational energy. Our focus in this research is on vibrational energy, which represents potential and kinetic energy possessed by molecules due to their motion, where this energy is quantized.

Molecular vibrations occur under the influence of the bond in terms of stretching and compressing, similar to the behavior of a spring that obeys Hooke's law. Therefore, this model is called the Simple Harmonic Oscillator model, which is an approximate model. The relation between vibrational potential energy and the internuclear distance is given by [4,5]:

$$V(r) = (1/2) K (r - r_e)^2 \quad (2)$$

Where $V(r)$ represents the potential energy, K is the force constant, r is the displacement, and r_e is the equilibrium bond length. The simplest molecules are diatomic molecules consisting of two atoms connected by a chemical bond vibrating along the axis between the nuclei. For approximation, the masses of the two nuclei can be taken as m_1 and m_2 , and the bond between them acts as a massless spring vibrating harmonically relative to the center of mass. According to Hooke's law, the restoring force is:

$$F = -k x \quad (3)$$

Where k is the force constant, and x is the displacement from the center of mass. Both masses can move together as an effective mass (μ), defined as:

$$\mu = (m_1 * m_2) / (m_1 + m_2) \quad (4)$$

The classical frequency of this oscillator is given by:

$$\nu = 1/2\pi \sqrt{k/\mu} \quad (5)$$

This equation describes the vibrational motion of the diatomic molecule with reduced mass μ vibrating under force k . According to quantum mechanics, Schrödinger's equation for this case is:

$$\left[\frac{-\hbar^2}{\mu} \nabla^2 + \frac{1}{2} k (r - r_e)^2 \right] \Psi = E \Psi \quad (6)$$

It is clear from solving this equation that the total vibrational energy is quantized and takes values:

$$E_{\text{vib}} = (v + 1/2) h \nu_{\text{vib}} \quad (7)$$

$$v = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Where ν_{vib} is the vibrational frequency, v is the vibrational quantum number, and h is Planck's constant equal to 6.625×10^{-34} Js. Since $\nu = c \omega$, the equation becomes:

$$E_{\text{vib}} = (v + 1/2) h c \omega \quad (8)$$

The equation can also be written in terms of the wavenumber, as commonly used in spectroscopy, after dividing by hc :

$$G(v) = W (v + 1/2) \quad (9)$$

Where W is the wavenumber in cm^{-1} (the classical natural frequency). The differences between vibrational energy levels in the harmonic oscillator model are equal to the classical natural frequency [6-8].

Regarding thermodynamics, which studies energy transformations of matter in space, these transformations lead to changes in internal energy levels, a type of potential energy within the system that plays a role in many concepts, including:

Heat of formation — a property related to the stability of the compound. If it is large and positive, the compound is unstable; if negative, the compound is stable. When most of the heat of formation is negative, it means forming the compound from its elements is generally exothermic (q or T), leading to greater stability since the heat content of the compound is less than the sum of the heat contents of its constituent elements.

Another important function is **entropy (S)**, which measures the randomness caused by temperature changes, given by:

$$ds = dq_r / T \quad (10)$$

Heat capacity, with units $\text{cal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{deg}^{-1}$, relates heat transferred to a substance and its temperature change by:

$$dQ = n C dT \quad (11)$$

Where dQ is the heat quantity, n the number of moles, C the heat capacity, and dT the temperature change. Heat capacity can also be written as:

$$R = C_P - C_V \quad (12)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, C_P is heat capacity at constant pressure, and C_V is heat capacity at constant volume. For nonlinear polyatomic molecules:

$$C_p = (3/2) R + (3N - 5) \quad (13)$$

Enthalpy (H) is an important function given by:

$$H = U - P V \quad (14)$$

Where H is enthalpy, U internal energy, P pressure, and V volume. Enthalpy depends on pressure, temperature, and energy for all materials except ideal or near-ideal gases. Its differential form is:

$$dH = du + P dv + V dP \quad (15)$$

The research importance lies in developing and determining the required thermal range for industrial materials better, relying on recent applied studies and sources [11].

The **dipole moment** is the electrostatic force acting between two equal but opposite charges; if the charge magnitude is q and distance is d, the dipole moment is given by [10]:

$$\mu = q \cdot d \quad (16)$$

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

To obtain results close to experimental data quickly, semi-empirical programs that require short calculation cycles were used. One advanced method used is the Modified Neglect of Differential Overlap Parameterization model 3 (MNDO-PM3), which achieves relatively high accuracy. The MNDO-PM3 method results showed good agreement with experimental data, motivating its use. These programs belong to molecular modeling software such as WinMopac7.21 and HyperChem8.0.

HyperChem8.0

This program relies on molecular mechanics modeling methods using simple analytical functions $f(r, \theta, \varphi)$, where φ is the torsion angle (bond length versus total molecular energy), r the bond length, and θ the angle between two atoms. To obtain the best balanced molecular geometry, a matrix containing internal coordinates is constructed, which serves as input for WinMopac7.21.

WinMopac7.21

The potential energy curve for the molecule is plotted by varying the bond length (H—F) and calculating total molecular energy at each step while fixing the bond, setting $opt=0$ instead of 1. This generates the potential energy curve, from which the bond length corresponding to minimum total energy (equilibrium position) is determined, and spectral properties are calculated.

RESULTS AND CALCULATIONS

Hydrogen Fluoride (HF) Molecule

The molecular structure of hydrogen fluoride (HF) was drawn using the HyperChem 8.0 program, which relies on internal coordinates (r, θ, φ). This represents the geometric structure of the molecule at its equilibrium state, as shown in Figure 1. After drawing the molecule and optimizing to obtain the best geometric configuration (Optimization), the initial molecular matrix is obtained. Table 1 contains the constituent atoms of the molecule, the interatomic distances, the optimal position of these atoms (Opt.), the bond angles (Angle), and the dihedral angles (Dihedral). After obtaining the initial matrix

and inputting it into WinMopac 7.21, several important properties were calculated, including binding energy, electronic energy, total energy, and repulsion energy. These properties and their units are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. Molecular Structure of Hydrogen Fluoride (HF) Molecule

Table 1. Initial Matrix for Hydrogen Fluoride (HF) Molecule

Atom	r(Å)	OPt	Θ (deg)	OPt	Φ(deg)	Opt
H	0.0000	0	0.0000	0	0.0000	0
F	1.0400	1	0.0000	0	0.0000	0

Table 2. Results of Important Calculated Properties for HF Molecule via HyperChem 8.0

Quantity	Magnitud	Unit
Total energy	-10525.8118	Kcal/mol
Total energy	-16.772353	a.u
Binding energy	-133.7558166	Kcal/mol
Isolated Atomic energy	-10391.05599	Kcal/mol
Electronic energy	-12220.38269	Kcal/mol
Core-core interaction	1695.570893	Kcal/mol
Heat of formation	-62.7638166	Kcal/mol
Zero point Energy	6.24524	Kcal/mol
Dipole Moment	-1.6500	-----

Anharmonic Potential Curve of the HF Molecule

After inputting the initial molecular matrix into WinMopac 7.21, optimization was performed for all atoms in the molecule. The H—F bond length was varied, and the corresponding total molecular energies were recorded to plot the potential energy curve. At the equilibrium distance ($r = r_e$), the minimum total energy was obtained as -133.755 eV at an equilibrium bond length of $r_e = 0.93$ Å. Around this point, the potential energy curve remains nearly stable as a straight line. The dissociation energy is approximately -131.454 eV, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Total Energy Variation with H—F Bond Distance for HF Molecule from WinMopac 7.21

Molecular Orbital Energy Eigenvalues for the HF Molecule

The molecular orbitals and their energy eigenvalues were calculated using the aforementioned programs. The number of occupied molecular orbitals was three, and one was unoccupied. The energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), denoted as E_{HOMO} , was computed, as well as the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), denoted as E_{LUMO} . These energy values, measured in electronvolts (eV), were used to determine the molecular orbital symmetry types. The energy gap was calculated using the relation $E_{\text{gap}} = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$, which was found to be 19.748 eV for the molecule, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Energy Levels of HF Molecule—Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital (E_{HOMO}), Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital (E_{LUMO}), and Symmetry of Each Orbital Calculated by HyperChem 8.0

Vibrational Frequencies and Modes of the HF Molecule

After calculating the potential energy for the HF molecule using HyperChem 8.0 and WinMopac 7.21, vibrational frequencies were computed in cm^{-1} , intensities in km/mol , and symmetries. The vibrational frequency is active in the infrared region. One vibrational frequency was calculated at 3067.70 cm^{-1} with an intensity of 49.972 km/mol according to the $(3N - 6)$ rule for linear molecules. The vibrational mode was described using HyperChem 8.0. Since the HF molecule is linear, one vibrational mode was calculated based on the $(N - 1)$ rule, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Vibrational Mode of HF Molecule, Frequency in cm^{-1} , Intensity in km/mol , Plotted via HyperChem 8.0

Calculation of Electrostatic Potential and Effective Charge of the HF Molecule

Several spectral properties of the HF molecule were calculated using HyperChem 8.0, including the total charge density in two and three dimensions, as shown in Figure 5. The electrostatic potential was also calculated in both 2D and 3D formats, as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Total Charge Density of HF Molecule in 2D and 3D

Figure 6. Electrostatic Potential of HF Molecule in 2D and 3D

Thermal Properties of the HF Molecule

Among the important properties calculated are the thermal properties that determine the key conditions under which reactions between molecules occur. Entropy was calculated, as shown in Figure 7, heat capacity as shown in Figure 8, heat of formation as shown in Figure 9, and enthalpy (thermal content) as shown in Figure 10 for the HF molecule at equilibrium, using WinMopac 7.21 after obtaining the final matrix from HyperChem 8.0.

Figure 7. Entropy (S) Versus Temperature (T) for HF Molecule

Figure 8. Heat Capacity (CP) Versus Temperature (T) for HF Molecule

Figure 9. Heat of Formation (H.O.F) Versus Temperature (T)

Figure 10. Enthalpy (H) Versus Temperature (T) for HF Molecule

CONCLUSIONS

The hydrogen fluoride (HF) molecule was studied and calculated using semi-empirical programs that require a short computational time for calculation cycles. Among these advanced semi-empirical methods used in this research are MNDO-PM3 to obtain thermal and spectral properties. This study was conducted upon obtaining the stable configuration of the molecule at the lowest total energy and at the equilibrium bond length r_e .

Figure 2 shows the relationship between bond length and dissociation energy. When the H—F bond is stretched, the atoms begin to separate, and the bonding energy between atoms decreases. The molecule typically dissociates when the bond length r increases beyond a certain limit.

The vibration of the HF molecule produces an oscillating dipole moment, resulting in a spectral line with high intensity.

The zero-point energy was calculated to be 6.24524 kcal/mol, indicating that the molecule experiences certain vibrations under normal conditions.

Vibrational frequencies depend strongly on the masses of the atoms; lighter atoms have higher vibrational frequencies, as described by the relation $1/2\pi \sqrt{(k/\mu)}$

From Figure 5, it is observed that most of the charge density is concentrated around the fluorine atom due to its higher electronegativity compared to hydrogen. This is because the attractive force is stronger, and electronegativity increases with atomic number. Therefore, the charge density surrounds fluorine.

Regarding Figure 6, due to the charge difference—the nucleus having positive charge and electrons negative there is a type of oscillation between them. Due to this displacement of positive and negative charges, the HF molecule behaves as a dipole. The molecular attraction is caused by electrostatic interactions between dipoles.

Fluorine is the most electronegative atom in the periodic table, while hydrogen is the least electronegative. This large difference causes fluorine to attract the shared electrons in the covalent bond more strongly than hydrogen.

The molecule has three occupied molecular orbitals and one unoccupied orbital. The energy gap was calculated to be $E_g=19.748$ eV

Thermal properties (entropy, enthalpy, and heat of formation) increase with temperature. This can be explained by increased translational and rotational motion, activation of molecular vibrations, breaking of intermolecular bonds, and increased randomness.

The heat capacity (C_P) is not affected by vibrational energy at normal temperatures (k), but at very high temperatures, C_P tends to stabilize. Therefore, the HF molecule is considered a simple, non-complex molecule because it contains only two atoms.

According to quantum mechanics, as molecular complexity increases, higher energy absorption and temperatures are required to cause changes in thermal properties. At low temperatures, translational and rotational motion contribute only to heat capacity. At higher temperatures, vibrational motion is taken into account. Thus, vibrational energy has little effect on the heat capacity of most gases at normal temperatures. However, as temperature rises, the number of molecules at different energy levels increases, causing heat capacity to increase with molecular complexity.

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